

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14934016

Effect Of Micro Electronic Banking On Operational Efficiency Of Deposit Money Banks In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study empirically examines effect of micro electronic banking on operational efficiency of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to; Investigate the effect of point of sale (POS), Automated teller machine (ATM) and mobile banking on the operational efficiency of deposit money bank in Nigeria. Three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated in line with the stated objectives. This study adopted ex-post facto research design and adopts a secondary approach in gathering data for the study. Descriptive research design was used in this study, the study scope ranged from 2014-2023. This study made use of secondary data. The data were sourced from publications of the Nigeria exchange group limited (NGE), the annual report and accounts of the listed banks from 2014-2023. The five (5) listed banks represent the sample size for this study. The study used panel least square as a method of data analysis. The variables used are point of sale (POS), automated teller machine (ATM), mobile banking and operational efficiency. The result of the study reveals that, Point of sales has a positive effect on deposit money bank operational efficiency in Nigeria. Mobility of payment has a positive effect and is statistically significant on deposit money bank. Automated teller machine has positive significant effect on the on deposit money bank in Nigeria. The study recommends that Advocate for more ATM facilities which should be placed at strategic location for easy access. Marketing and education of internet banking service and products should be intensified to attract more customers which enhance profitability.

Keywords: point of sale (POS), operational efficiency, Automated teller machine, mobile banking

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Electronic banking refers to the use of information technology in banking activities (Adrian, 2019). Electronic banking is the use of electronic and telecommunication networks to deliver a wide range of value added products and services to bank customers (Atueyi, Nkechukwu. & Nzotta, & Jacobs, 2019). In recent years, the banking industry has tapped into opportunities offered by technology and leveraged its capabilities into service. Banks have eschewed their conventional roles in favor of innovation, improvement, and the launch of new service categories to meet the changing needs of their clientele. The operations of large commercial banks have seen a great deal of innovation and diversification. Electronic Banking (e-banking) has opened up a new channel of banking through the internet which has provided an avenue for new forms of business processes within value chains creating more innovative ways of linking with customers and collaborating with partners.

Electronic banking is when electronic and telecommunication networks are employed to deliver a wide range of value-added products and services to bank customers (Osang, 2017). Electronic banking is the engagement of information technology in banking operations. Electronic banking, stemming from the realm of e-commerce within banking and financial sectors, enables banks to provide payment services for their customers engaging in online shopping. This platform allows customers to conduct banking

transactions electronically, eliminating the need for physical visits to traditional bank branches (Obi-Nwosu, Onuoha, and Okoye, 2021). Electronic banking may be described as a means by which banking products and services are provided through electronic devices such as phones, iPods, etc. The nascent advances in technology seen around the world have eliminated the traditional manual banking system and brought about a paradigm shift in banking to the extent that banks are using internet technologies to improve efficiency and scale up the provision of a wide range of value-added products and services. Consequently, Nigerian banks, especially commercial ones, now identify electronic banking as a unique means of differentiating themselves from their rivalries by investing in complicated expertise in order to sustain their bank growth (Amaduche, Adesanya, and Adediji, 2020).

In the past, this part of banking has remained at the infant level (Ovia, 2021). This is the case despite the fact that Internet banking has several advantages over visiting a physical bank location. Lack of suitable operational facilities, such as communications and electricity, upon which electronic banking depends, has been noted as a contributing factor to the inability of banks in Nigeria to fully take advantage of this mode of banking (Akinduko, 2020). Internet banking is seen as less important in the current banking system since banks have not been able to integrate their operations into the internet development process, but the advent of CBN cashless policy has made electronic banking necessary for every individual, firms or corporate organizations in Nigeria. It has been previously stated that the lack of a clearly defined legal framework for internet banking, leaving banks with inadequate legal cover to provide the services, and poor telecommunication infrastructural support are contributing factors to internet banking's moderate economic impact in Nigeria. The fact that fraudsters have exploited the country's internet system makes it a less desirable location for genuine foreign and local financial transactions (Atueyi, .Nkechukwu, & Jacobs 2019).

A rising body of data suggests that fraudulent Nigerians utilize spurious websites to steal money from unsuspecting victims around the globe, adding to the natural skepticism that exists about using online banking services in Nigeria (Victory et al, 2022). Existing bank locations are sometimes used for these kinds of crimes. However, the banking sector's use of digital technology to carry out everyday duties has recently seen some major advancement. This study aims to determine whether or not there is a substantial correlation between the adoption of digital accounting techniques and the financial operational efficiency of Nigeria's publicly traded financial institutions. Specifically, the study aimed at investigating the relationship between block chain technology and return on assets (ROA) of Nigerian deposit money banks that are publicly traded, and to determine whether cloud-based accounting has any relationship with ROA of Nigeria's publicly traded deposit money banks.

1.2 Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the examines the effect of micro electronic banking on operational efficiency of deposit money banks in Nigeria , while the specific objectives are to:

1. Investigate the effect of point of sale (POS) on operational efficiency of deposit money bank in Nigeria.
2. Examine the effect of automated teller machine (ATM) on the operational efficiency of deposit money bank in Nigeria
3. Evaluate the effect of mobile banking on the operational efficiency of deposit money bank in Nigeria

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURES

2. 1 Theoretical Review

The Theory of Innovation Diffusion

Rogers (1962) propounded that innovation diffusion is based on the notion that the adoption of innovation involves the spontaneous or planned spread of new ideas and Rogers defines an innovation as 'an idea, practice, or object that is perceived as new (Rogers 1995). He stressed that it is the perception of change that is important; if the idea seems new to the potential adopter, then it should be considered to be an innovation. Rogers (1995) approaches the topic of innovation diffusion by considering a variety of case studies on topics including controlling scurvy in the British Navy, diffusion of hybrid corn in Iowa,

diffusion of the news, bottle feeding of babies in the third world, how the refrigerator got its hum, Xerox PARC and Apple computer, black music in white America, Minitel in France, the non-diffusion of the Dvorak keyboard, and causes of the Irish potato famine.

In diffusion theory, the existence of innovation is seen to cause uncertainty in the minds of potential adopters (Berlyne, 1962), and uncertainty implies a lack of predictability and information. Diffusion is considered to be an information exchange process amongst members of a communicating social network driven by the need to reduce uncertainty (Rogers, 1995). Those involved in considering the adoption of the innovation are motivated to seek information to reduce this uncertainty (Rogers, 1995). Diffusion theory contends that a technological innovation embodies information, and so its adoption acts to reduce uncertainty. In illustration of this Rogers cites the innovation of solar panels as reducing uncertainty over future energy costs and reliability of energy supply. The new ideas upon which an innovation is based are communicated over time, through various types of communication channels, among the members of a social system. There are thus four main elements of any theory of innovation diffusion: characteristic of the innovation itself, the nature of the communication channels, the passage of time, and the social system through which the innovation diffuses (Rogers, 1995).

2.2 Empirical Review

Abbas, (2024) investigated the multifaceted impact of electronic banking on Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. The study's hypotheses were formulated to ascertain the significance of electronic banking adoption on DMBs' financial performance. Rooted in the Technology Acceptance Model, the study employed a longitudinal approach, observing licensed commercial banks in Nigeria through a census method and utilizing secondary data analysis. The analytical model assessed the impact of ATM, POS, and mobile banking on bank performance, utilizing equations to evaluate Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Assets (ROA). Findings revealed that various electronic banking methods significantly influence a bank's financial performance. Notably, POS transactions demonstrated the most substantial impact on ROE, while mobile banking exhibited the least. The study suggested strategies for banks to optimize performance, emphasizing reducing certain transaction volumes while enhancing others through different electronic banking channels. This study, thus, provides critical insights into electronic banking's intricate dynamics, offering valuable guidance for industry stakeholders and policymakers to optimize operations, enhance customer experiences, and drive sustainable growth in the digital banking landscape.

Ojianwuna (2024) examined the audited financial statements of 10 deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange in 2011–2020 to extract secondary data. As well as journals, textbooks, and the CBN Bulletin, other public resources were used for the study. The findings revealed that e-banking had a positive and significant effect on the performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria, as measured by Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), Point of Sales (POS), Internet Banking (IB), and Mobile Banking (MB), as measured by return on equity (ROE) and return on assets (ROA) (ROA). On the other hand, e-banking does not significantly affect Earnings per Share (EPS).

Dauda and Haruna, (2024) examined the effect of electronic banking on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Although electronic banking has been in existence in Nigeria for some years now, its contributions to the performance of deposit money banks remained debatable. Anchored on the theory of innovation diffusion, this study used secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement System (NIBSS). Data analysis was done using the OLS regression model to test the relationship between electronic banking aspects of web transactions and mobile transactions, and the performance of deposit money banks measured via loans and advances and private sector deposits. The findings showed that both web and mobile transactions do not affect loans and advances and private sector deposits. Thus, the study concluded that electronic banking failed to influence the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Ogbonna, et. al., (2023) examined financial technology and the operational efficiency of the financial institutions in Sub-Saharan African economies from 2005-2021. This is due to findings that fin-tech evolutions do not comply with financial institution regulations and their engagement in regulatory

arbitrage. The study attempts to ascertain the implication of financial technology on financial institution operational efficiency in Sub-Saharan African economies. The broad objective of this study is to examine financial technology's effect on the financial institutions' operational efficiency of selected Sub-Saharan African countries. The study collated data from both the Central Bank of the selected countries and the World Bank Development Indicator (WDI) of various years, and were subjected to the panel data regression analysis. The results revealed a strongly significant impact of financial technology on the operational efficiency of the financial institution in the Sub-Saharan African economies.

Harmadi, Wisnu, Irwan, and Atmaji (2022) examined the effect of Fintech on the operational efficiency and risk of conventional banks in Indonesia. The proxy for fintech in this study is P2P lending and the adoption of fintech technology by banks. The number of conventional banks in Indonesia is 107 banks, and this study took a sample of 81 conventional banks. This research period is for 5 years from 2017 to 2021. The results show that P2P lending and fintech adoption do not affect the operational efficiency or risk of conventional banks. However, what is interesting about the results of this study is that the interaction between each independent variable with the moderating variable of bank ownership structure shows the results of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable which is significant. We find that bank ownership structure is proven to strengthen the effect of P2P lending and fin-tech adoption on bank risk, while the effect on operational efficiency is not significant. We found that the presence of P2P lending will increase the risk of conventional banks. While the effect of fin-tech adoption shows a lowering effect on bank risk, especially those owned by cooperatives. Our findings support previous research results that the presence of P2P lending will increase bank risk, and the adoption of fin-tech will decrease risk.

Kamo, Danny, Sune, Johnny and Ruschelle (2022) determined the relationship between financial technology and commercial banks' financial operational efficiency. A simple linear regression was used along with descriptive analysis and correlation analysis based on the top five banks in South Africa. Two measures of financial operational efficiency, return on equity and return on assets, were utilized using secondary bank data for the period of 2011-2021. The findings indicated that within the chosen sample period, there is a relationship between the financial operational efficiency of the top five banks in South Africa and the incorporation of financial technology led by the number of mobile subscriptions used for internet banking. Findings also showed that competition within the banking sector is emerging, meaning that South Africa's banking sector is moving from an oligopolistic environment into a more competitive one. This may be viable for experts within the banking space as it can provide substantial evidence that the transition from traditional-based banking to a more digital approach will be to their benefit in terms of financial operational efficiency and gaining market share within the sector.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Population of the Study

The population of the study is made up to eighteen quoted banks in Nigeria exchange group limited as at 31st Dec 2014 to 2023 which is twenty-four in number.

3.2 Sample Size and Sampling Method

The five (5) listed banks represent the sample size for this study. Data were gathered from the published financial statements of the five (5) listed banks for a ten (10) year period spanning from 2014-2023, using purposive sampling method (that is selected firms that filed their annual financial statements with NEG from 2014-2023 without missing any year was selected for this study). The total number of quoted banks in Nigeria exchange group limited were twenty-four (24), the researcher choose five banks from them, Access bank, Zenith bank, UBA, First Bank, and Union, fidelity bank, and FCMB because of proximity.

3.3 Model Specification

The study adopted the model of Atueyi Nkechukwu. and Nzotta, S.M & Jacobs, C.J (2019) who examine Effect of electronic banking on small and medium scale enterprise in Nigeria.

$$ROA = F(\text{POS, ATM, MB, INTB}) \text{ -----Equ (1)}$$

Where

ROA = Return on assets

POS = Point of sales

ATM = Automated teller machine

MB = Mobile banking

INTB = Internet banking

The present study adopted the model and modifies it

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 POS + \beta_2 ATM + \beta_3 MB \text{ -----Equ (2)}$$

ROA= Return on equity (proxy of operational efficiency of bank)

POS= Point of sale

ATM= Automated teller Machine

MB= Mobile banking

Bo= constant

β_1 - β_3 is parameters to be estimated

3.4 Variables and Measurement

Variable	measurement	Authorities
Dependent Variable Return on Assets	This is measured as net profit after tax divided by total assets in this study	Horst, Kutts, Chreuter, & Gutteir, (2007).
Independent Variable Point of sale	Measured by the total amount of transactions done through POS on an annual basis	Hoseiniande & Dangoliani, (2015). Ichniowski, & Giovanna. (2011).
Automate teller machine	This is measured by the annual turnover on the total number of transactions carried out via ATM channels.	Ivatury, & Pickens, (2006).
Mobile banking	Measured by the total number of banking transaction done through phone on an annual basis.	Ivatury, & Pickens, (2006).

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS PRESENTATION

4.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the empirical results and discussion of findings. Panel Least Square (OLS) was used as statistical tools for the analysis. The result was subjected to different statistical and descriptive tests.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Here, the individual characteristics of the variables used in this study were presented. The aim of descriptive statistics is to examine the operational efficiency of the variables within the review period. The descriptive statistics is presented in table 4.1 below.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics

	ROA	POS	MOP	ATM
Mean	16.31544	6.914620	17.63386	5.954700
Median	16.41571	7.153896	17.91208	6.002899
Maximum	19.50550	10.28997	20.59033	8.776490
Minimum	13.73023	2.400619	14.28619	3.220874
Std. Dev.	1.496468	1.933643	2.028058	1.855737
Skewness	0.036441	-0.496451	-0.179059	0.006634
Kurtosis	2.033288	3.067970	1.524361	1.407504
Jarque-Bera	1.370606	1.444440	3.362565	3.698653
Probability	0.503937	0.485673	0.186135	0.157343
Sum	571.0405	242.0117	617.1849	208.4145
Sum Sq. Dev.	76.14014	127.1251	139.8427	117.0879
Observations	50	50	50	50

Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables for the study. It presents the standard deviation, mean maximum and minimum values of the data set obtained from the annual reports. Return on equity, which showed a maximum value of 19.5% and a minimum value of 13.7% with a mean value of 16.3% and standard deviation of 1.4%. The Point of sales maximum value of ratio is 10.28% while the minimum value is 2.4%. The mean obtained from the computation gave 6.9% with a standard deviation of 1.9%. The mobility of payment showed a maximum value of 20% and a minimum value of 14.2% with a mean value of 17.6% and standard deviation of 2.0%. Automated teller machine has a maximum value of 8.7% and a minimum value of 3.2%. The mean value obtained was 5.9% with a standard deviation of 1.8%.

4.2 Tests For Multicollinearity

The term multicollinearity is due to Ragnar Frisch. Originally, it meant the existence of a „perfect“ or exact, linear relationship among some or all explanatory variables of a regression model. The tests were carried out using correlation matrix. According to Barry and Feldman (1985) criteria; „Multicollinearity is not a problem if not correlation exceeds 0.80“

Table 4.2 Result of Multicollinearity Text

	ROA	POS	MOP	ATM
LFP	1.000000	0.348408	-0.104480	-0.240269
LPOS	0.348408	1.000000	0.832452	0.743984
LMOP	-0.104480	0.832452	1.000000	0.977133
LATM	-0.240269	0.743984	0.977133	1.000000

From the table above it was observed that there is no problem of Multicollinearity on the variables because no variables exceeds 80% as Feldman 1985 noted

4.3 Regression Result

Dependent Variable: ROA
 Method: Panel EGLS (Period random effects)
 Date: 03/03/25 Time: 09:43
 Sample: 2014 2023
 Periods included: 10
 Cross-sections included: 5
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 50
 Swamy and Arora estimator of component variances

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	24.17950	3.804105	6.356161	0.0000
POS	0.853013	0.154773	5.511394	0.0000
MOP	0.041298	0.367814	2.831044	0.0087
ATM	0.772462	0.352180	2.193372	0.0371

Effects Specification		S.D.	Rho
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)			
Period random		0.000000	0.0000
Idiosyncratic random		0.462722	1.0000

Weighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.897933	Mean dependent var	16.31544
Adjusted R-squared	0.871471	S.D. dependent var	1.496468
S.E. of regression	0.536498	Sum squared resid	7.771405
F-statistic	33.93312	Durbin-Watson stat	1.904259
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Unweighted Statistics	
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R-squared	0.897933	Mean dependent var	16.31544
Sum squared resid	7.771405	Durbin-Watson stat	0.904259

Interpretation of the Result

The R^2 which is the coefficient of determination or the measure of goodness of fit shows the degree of variation in the dependent variables, as explained by the independent variables all taken together. The closer our R^2 is to 1, the better the goodness of fit of the model. From the result in table 4.3 above, we found out that our $R^2 = 0.897933$. This is closer to 1 and thus indicates that our model displayed a good fit. The adjusted $R^2 = 0.87$ this implies that despite the adjustment in the degree of freedom our variables can still explain about 87% of the changes or variation in the model. Thus, it is in line with the result of the goodness of fit of the model.

The f-statistics is used to test the overall statistical significance of our parameter in the model. If the probability of F in the computed model is greater than the desired level of significance (0.5) we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative. From the result in table 4.3 above the computed value of f is 33.93312 while its probability is 0.00000. Since its probability is less than 0.05 we accept alternative hypothesis which states that the independent variables are jointly statistically significant in explaining the dependent variable.

The Durbin Watson statistic is used to test for the presence or otherwise of autocorrelation in our regression model. When the value of our d-w statistics is 2, it means the absence of autocorrelation among the explanatory variables in the model.

The a priori expectation is determined by the existing economic theory and it indicates the signs of the economic relationship under consideration. From the result of our estimated model it was discovered that point of Sale has a positive sign given its value as 0.853013. This implies that increase point of sale in increase the operational efficiency of the selected banks bank by 8%.

Automated teller machine has positive sign given its value as 0.772462, this means that increase in automated teller machine increase the operational efficiency of the selected banks bank by 0.7%, and this conforms to our a priori expectation. Mobility of payment has a positive sign given its value as 0.041298. This suggests increase in bank operational efficiency by 1 This conforms to our theoretical expectation.

The t-statistics, this helps in detecting the individual statistical significance of parameter from the model. It was discovered that both automated teller machine and point of sale are positive and statistically significant, which implies that they contributed to bank operational efficiency. However, Mobility of payment (MOP) is positive and statistically significant at 5% level.

4.3 Hypothesis Testing

Ho₁: Point of sale has no significant effect on the operational efficiency of commercial bank in Nigeria.

From the result of our test in table 4.3 above, we found out that the value of our t-test for Point of sale is 5.511394 with a probability of 0.000; this probability value is greater than the desired level of significance (0.05). We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, which says that Point of sale has significant effect on the operational efficiency of commercial bank in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Automated teller machine has no significant effect on the operational efficiency of commercial bank in Nigeria.

From the result of our test in the table 4.3 above, we found out the value of our T-test for ATM is 2.193372 with a probability of 0.0371, this probability value is greater than the desired level of significance (0.05). We reject the null and accept the alternative hypothesis, which says that Automated teller machine has significant effect on the operational efficiency of commercial bank in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: Mobile banking has no significant effect on the operational efficiency of commercial bank in Nigeria.

T-test for Mobile banking is 2.831044 with a probability of 0.0087; this probability value is greater than the desired level of significance (0.05). We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, which says that Mobile banking has significant effect on the operational efficiency of commercial bank in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The importance of the adoption of micro electronic banking to operational efficiency of deposit money bank is high. Importance of adequacy in infrastructure which was identified to be required for adoption of POS in rural areas, there are other known variables that contributed positively to the adoption of POS in rural areas these includes POS security, customer trust, customer education, and customer motivation. It has been identified that the adoption of artificial intelligence in an organization was prompted by the quest for the use of an alternative mode of payments to the use of cash, as it is the main medium of exchange for goods and services in rural areas. The choice of artificial intelligence which is a device for electronic payments systems was also to reduce the risk involved in carrying cash and the attendant consequence having known that this device is used basically for processing payments. The adoption of artificial intelligence in Nigeria reduces the volume of cash to be printed by the agency responsible for the printing. The reduction of the amount of money spent in cash management can be channeled to other uses. In conclusion artificial intelligence has a significant positive effect on the operational efficiency of deposit money bank in Nigeria. Based on the following findings of this study, the following policy recommendations are suggested: The researcher Advocate for more ATM facilities which should be placed at strategic location for easy access. Marketing and education of internet banking service and products should be intensified to attract more customers which enhance profitability. The bank should conduct more research to find new internet banking product to attract and to retain her potential customers.

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